

**RECYCLING
POST-CONSUMER
FIBREBOARD AND
SOLID WOOD
WASTE INTO NEW
FIBREBOARDS
(HDF)**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating end-of-life panels into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

APPLICATIONS

High-density fibreboard (HDF) is a wood-based panel with excellent stability and a smooth finish for demanding applications.

Used in flooring, door applications and furniture, including back panels, drawer bottoms and lightweight components such as board on frame and board on style.

ACHIEVEMENTS

Industrial trial 1: fibres from post-consumer fibreboards extracted through Dieffenbacher's wet process

- Outcome: up to 15% recycled fibres in thin HDF with no impact on production line productivity, surface quality and paintability.
- Limitation: bending strength and internal bond decreased because the industrial testing did not allow for gluing the recycled fibres before blending.

Industrial trial 2: fibres from post-consumer solid wood extracted through conventional thermo-mechanical pulping

- Outcome: up to 25% recycled fibres with mechanical and swelling performance comparable to reference panels; production speed slightly declined with increased content.
- Limitation: impurities appeared on the panel surface, indicating need for improvement through additional sifting and cleaning.

FUTURE CHALLENGES

- Secure a steady supply of quality wood waste at sufficient volumes.
- Modernise existing plants with optimised sorting lines.
- Upgrade sifting and cleaning in fibreboard production lines.
- Optimise production process, especially how recycled fibres are introduced.

PARTNERS

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